

Integrity policies in public management during the pandemic: Experiences of public officials

By

Ramón Huiman Yerrén

Magíster en Gestión Pública, Universidad César Vallejo, Perú

hyerrenr@ucvvirtual.edu.pe

ORCID: 0000-0002-3087-6375

Blanca Elcira Carranza Guerrero

Magíster en Educación con mención en Docencia y Gestión Educativa, Universidad César Vallejo, Perú

cguerrerob@ucvvirtual.edu.pe

ORCID: 0000-0002-5043-9201

Carmen Graciela Arbulú Pérez Vargas

Doctora en Educación, Universidad César Vallejo, Perú

carbulu@ucvvirtual.edu.pe

ORCID: 0000-0002-8463-6553

Abstract

The article “Integrity policies in public management during the pandemic: Experiences of civil servants” arises to strengthen the preventive, sanctioning and risk management capacity against acts of corruption that affect civil servants and public servants, as well as institutional governance and public service. The general objective was to propose a theoretical model of public integrity to prevent and strengthen ethical behaviors in public servants and civil servants of social health insurance under behavioral economics and ethical governance. A methodology with a qualitative approach, the hermeneutic phenomenological design, was used with interviews that revealed the experiences of officials who lived tensions during the health emergency, identifying and interpreting categories and subcategories that affect the national policy of public integrity. The results reveal practices and behaviors that do not conform to the framework of public integrity, little promotion of meritocracy when appointing officials, behaviors that do not conform to integrity in the contracting of goods, services and personnel, little support for officials who act following standards, the little culture of integrity, weak anti-corruption system, favoring of suppliers, pressure from officials and advisors, feelings of indignation and discomfort due to unethical behavior.

Keywords: Ethical governance, behavioral economics, corruption, public officials’ experience, public management, integrity.

Introduction

Integrity is the quality of a human being that follows moral considerations; an integral person is committed and unconditional (Honderich, 2013). Conversely, corruption is a negative phenomenon causing significant damage to the development of institutions; it is a problem that affects stability, democratic values and national security (Inshyn et al., 2021); what goes wrong in politics and government is the abuse of power for personal gain including bribery, favoritism, fraud, theft, conflict of interest and gifts (Huberts et al., 2022). Public management in Peru reflects a crisis of values affecting governance, so it is necessary to create circles of

Published/ publié in *Res Militaris* (resmilitaris.net), vol.12, n°4, December Issue 2022

transparency, present management reports within the legal framework to combat acts that violate norms, develop social responsibility programs, and strengthen education in values (Valeriano, 2019). This also requires that the public function should be depoliticized to promote values, ethics, and morals and enhance complaints (Oyango, 2021).

This research was carried out taking into account the background of the case of the Odebrecht company revealed in December 2016 in Peru, which operated through acts of corruption to obtain illicit concessions (Hennings, 2020); the purpose is to establish procedures to measure and monitor the conduct of public servants and officials (Ponce, 2019).

In the evaluation made in the year 2021 by the General Comptroller of the Republic of Peru, in a Press Release of July 6, 2022, it determined that Peru lost in the year more than 24 billion soles due to corruption, which represents 13.6% of the national budget (Comptroller's Office, 2022). In social networks of June 22, 2019, it was disseminated that the Health Social Security, through senior management officials, have been manipulating fractional purchases (Hospital Almenara, 2019). During the health emergency on June 30, 2020, it refers that corruption comes from the upper echelons and on October 19, 2022, it reported contracts in favor of a company in the implementation of hospitals to serve patients with Covid, linked to an official (Prado, 2022).

From an approach to the problematic reality, this situation occurs due to deficiencies in ethical governance, deficient mechanisms to manage complaints, non-compliance with regulations, deficiencies in the commitment of the heads and chiefs to disseminate ethical commitments, limitations to the culture of integrity, discrepancies among officials, political pressures from the highest hierarchical level to favor certain companies with the contracting of goods, services or hiring of personnel that do not meet the competencies, are factors that aggravate the situation mentioned above. Therefore, it is important to gather information on the employees' experiences from the approach of behavioral economics and ethical governance; to know the human essence understood as something unique, integral, free, rational, with dignity and rights (Polo, 2003).

The main research question was formulated in the following terms: How did civil servants experience the performance of public integrity during the Covid-19 health emergency in a social health insurance hospital? And how can one propose a theoretical model of public integrity to prevent and strengthen ethical behavior in public and civil servants? This question is intended to enter into the understanding of subjectivity.

Officials make important decisions regarding hiring personnel, goods and services to fulfill their missionary role, posing the following research questions: What experiences did the officials go through in the processes of tension and what were their actions during the Covid-19 health emergency for the framework of Public Integrity? What are the factors that, according to the perspective of the officials, affect their administrative actions in the framework of public integrity? How can the proposed theoretical model from the behavioral economics approach and ethical governance contribute to strengthening the Integrity policy's implementation? How can the theoretical model be validated from the approach of behavioral economics and ethical governance?

Thus, the general objective was: To propose a theoretical model of public integrity to prevent and strengthen ethical behavior in social health insurance employees and civil servants under behavioral economics and ethical governance. In addition, the following specific objectives were proposed: i) To unveil the experiences and experiences that officials went

through in the stress processes during the Covid-19 health emergency; for the framework of Public Integrity; ii) To interpret the experiences and experiences of the officials by identifying the factors that affect them according to the perspective of the officials and that affect their behavior in the framework of public integrity; iii) Identify the theoretical and methodological foundations that support the proposal of a theoretical model from the approach of behavioral economics and ethical governance; iv) Design a theoretical model proposal from the approach of behavioral economics and ethical governance that contributes to the strengthening of the Integrity policy; v) Validate the theoretical model based on the approach of behavioral economics and ethical governance through the Delphi method.

Theoretical Framework

Integrity in public service considers aspects such as recognizing, raising awareness, deliberating on the need for ethics, formulating programs and action plans, and having management tools and legal and regulatory frameworks. It is the integrity based on which society and citizens can bet on the quality of institutions and their officials (Hoekstra et al., 2022).

Integrity projects meaning and quality in human life.

Llanes and Salvador (2018) argue that the ethical dimension of public integrity is based on ethical principles and values, which constitute rules and norms of behavior and values. Ethical behavior is indispensable to transforming the paradigm of sustainable development. Canales (2002) points out that ethics and integrity in the public function are at the service of the public and are rewarding when it is oriented to the achievement of the common good. The basic condition of human beings is their vulnerability to be hurt, suffer damage or harm; public servants serve the vulnerable (Ausín 2019).

Integrity in public service is the product of a decision-making process influenced by concepts such as self-esteem, age, gender, the organization's culture and the workers' professional profiles (Columbié, 2017). The code of conduct regulates the actions of civil and public servants in public service and promotes the values that stand out in the institution. The performance of public servants based on values, principles and duties guarantee professionalism, efficiency and effectiveness in public service (Zamora-Leclère, 2009).

For Diego (2018), the most ethical countries are those that support education and the application of ethical instruments and work to control corruption. Establishing transparent and orderly public institutions are consistent with the state modernization policy (Tapia et al., 2022). Acting unethically prevents achieving the institutional objective; it violates transparency, accountability, citizen participation, and collaborative innovation (Arroyo, 2018). Diaz (2018) refers that public servants attach significant importance to the public management model based on ethics and governance principles. The Ibero-American Charter of Ethics and Integrity for the Public Service establishes that concrete objectives and policies are designed based on the axes of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and National Plans or Strategies (Rothstein and Sorak, 2017).

Scholars around the world have argued that, for ethics management and anti-corruption, controls based on regulatory compliance and ethical program integrity are indispensable (Hoekstra and Kaptein, 2014; Huberts, 2014; Huberts and Six, 2012).

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the 2030 agenda leads to take a look at SDG No. 16, which promotes peaceful and inclusive societies and its goals that aim to reduce

corruption in all its forms, the generation of transparent institutions with accountability, adopt decisions that are inclusive, participatory and responsive to the needs and public access to information. Furthermore, the Integrity studies of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development OECD help formulate public policies to improve them, adopt good practices, and promote principles and standards; on policies (OECD, 2018).

The National Agreement (2021) in Peru comprises 35 policies, National Policy No. 24 affirms an Efficient and Transparent State and seeks a commitment to build and make possible an efficient, effective, modern and transparent nation at the service of the people and their rights and National Policy No. 26, seeks to promote Ethics and Transparency, eradicate corruption, end money laundering, combat Tax evasion and Smuggling.

Taking into account the above, the “Humanistic Theory of administration” is considered the general theory for this research, and the substantive theories are the “theory of the new public management” and the “governance theory”. The Humanistic Theory of Administration empowers the human capacity of an organization; the individual feels fulfilled. Mendoza (2018) conceives as an individual or collective creation and construction or as historical dynamics in the framework of a discursive activity involving theories, authors and followers of a scientific community.

The New Public Management theory emerged as a series of principles of general philosophy and as opposed to bureaucracy (Noël, 2019) to have institutions with efficient administrative models, with a new structural and administrative model (Restrepo, 2017), which represents a model that incorporates private sector principles in the public sector (Sánchez and Liendo, 2020). It is a dynamic way of structuring, managing and supervising institutions, including government leaders and public policies (Barzelay, 2003). Subsequently, the New Public Management leads to a rethink of the interaction between public, private and social actors (Peters, 2010). Emerging the new Governance Model is achieved through collaborative work and achieving common goals (Mendoza and Vernis, 2008).

Governance originates from criticism of the new public management (Reyes and Ortiz, 2018). As a product of two different sectors such as i) Corporate governance, which is based on concretizing economic objectives through stakeholder processes, and ii) good governance, focused on transparency, decision making and accountability (Jolly, 2005). Collaborative governance involves stakeholders’ participation, including authorities, citizens, civil society and the private sector (Palacios et al., 2021). This makes it possible to manage the risks to which the institution is exposed, which means identifying, analyzing, evaluating and treating; better managing the corruption problem (Monteduro et al., 2021). It is a form of governance that emerged in neoliberal capitalism (Puello-Socarrás, 2018). The contributions to the administration as a model of public management strengthen effectiveness and efficiency in the quality and control of public affairs (Olivera Robles et al., 2017). Integrity policies are considered elements for the governance of public entities Portal (2016).

The approach to ethical governance and public values is based on virtues; integrity is defined as a practice of public professionals that must be integrated (Van Stadem, 2022). Ethical governance directs the activity of the state to achieve social justice, which translates into equal opportunities for human development and the possibility of accessing quality public services (Portal, 2016). Good governance corresponds to good government and is based on respect for rules and good practices (Maldonado, 2018; Modzom, 2017; Herrera, 2016).

Self-regulation through codes of conduct of the institution related to ethical governance, given that law, does not always fall under ethics, nor does it deal with ethically reprehensible conduct (Jimenez, 2017). Public integrity studies require a reflective perspective on public governance, because efficiency is excellent but do not forget to measure integrity (Trommell, 2020). Governance as normative combines moral principles such as participation, fairness, equality, accountability and legitimacy (Hajer et al., 2004) and (Kersbergen et al., 2001). Governance is improving citizens' quality of life and achievements due to the public policy implemented (Bovarid and Loffter, 2003).

Ethical governance is an approach related to power, politics, authority, administration, management, direction, government, and organization (Bevir, 2009; Fukuyama, 2016, Rose-Ackerman, 2017). Its perspective is the formulation of public policies that solve collective problems (Huberts, 2014); with the participation of public and private actors. When integrity is violated, it impacts organizational governance (Lasthuizen et al., 2011). Ethical governance is to pay attention to moral values and norms and formulate and implement policies; the crucial point is to define the integrity policy and the fight against corruption that should be considered in the public agenda (Vardi & Weitz, 2004). Integrity refers to the ethics of behavior; ethics of governance and ethics theory include ethics in policies and societal outcomes (Huberts, 2014).

Daniel Kahneman's behavioral economics approach, as a theory of human relations, highlights how humans decide what is most convenient for institutions (Kahneman and Smith, 2002). Behavioral economics for two decades has evidenced academic contributions in the design and execution of public policies, which contributes to decision-making under risks (Sanchez, 2018). The work teams participate in the development and implementation of strategies at all levels of government (Svitlana et al., 2019). It recognizes that corruption and lack of integrity is a problem of culture. Therefore, some tools can help solve it (Molano, 2016); from the findings, Behavioral Economics can detect and combat corruption. On the other hand, Ferrando (2016) argues that it results in increased public spending, erosion of the image of the political system, deteriorated competitiveness and affected the country's external image.

Method

The type of research is basic (Esteban, 2018) and contributes to universal knowledge. It is framed within the qualitative approach and underlies the relevance assumed from the paradigm that focuses on understanding the hermeneutic phenomena, which explore from the gaze of the investigated participants. For Lincoln and Guba (2002), from the epistemological assumption, the researcher and the researched object are interactively linked, and the researcher's values influence the research; reality is understood in the research.

The research design is hermeneutic phenomenological; due to its qualitative approach, it uses descriptive information, small groups such as communities, institutions, etc. (Tamayo, 1999). According to existentialist phenomenologists, phenomenology and Hermeneutics (FH) is a design applied to human sciences (Levering and Van Manen, 2002). It extends to humanities; its research model is based on experience (Barnacle, 2004). It explores, describes, and understands people's experiences of phenomena; phenomenology is a research philosophy, approach, and design. Researchers conduct it directly with statements, maybe feelings, emotions, reasons, and fears (Silverman, 2018; Wertz et al., 2011; Norlyk and Harder, 2010). The categories are detailed in the matrix below (Table 1):

Table 1 *Matrix of categories and subcategories*

Analysis Categories	Subcategories of Analysis	Data collection techniques	Data collection instruments
Practices and behaviors within the framework of integrity	Poor dissemination of ethics and integrity. Unethical behavior.	Interview Documentary review	Conversation Guide Documentary matrix
	Appointment of an official not based on merit. Weakness in contracting integrity. Little support for ethical and integral action. Weak anti-corruption system. Pressure received from bosses or advisors.		
Experiences within the framework of integrity	Favorable hiring conditions. Feelings of indignation and discomfort.	Interview Documentary review	Conversation Guide Documentary matrix
	Deficiencies in actions during the pandemic. Actions to promote integrity.		

Note: *Prepared by the authors.*

Codes were used to describe the environment and the participants (Creswell, 2013), carried out in the administrative areas of the Red Prestacional Lambayeque, collecting experiences of the participants for the research categories; they came into contact with the phenomenon through interviews; during the process, interpretations are made, being able to change with it the constructed object (Saavedra and Castro, 2007).

The inclusion criteria for the sample were seven employees who provided their experiences and perceptions. The sampling was done conveniently because it helps an appropriate sample for the researcher (Hernández et al., 2014). The interview technique was used; there were similar responses; it was interpreted with non-numerical processing (Hernández and Mendoza, 2018). A conversation guide was used (Scheele and Groeben, 1988). It allowed information collection through semi-structured and open-ended questions (Arias, 2012). A conversation is exhibited, adjusting to the experiences to be known (Taller, 2017), and seeking a response from the facts (Palacios and Corral, 2010).

To develop the qualitative research protocol (Troncoso and Amaya, 2017). The following were taken into consideration: a) The place where the interview was conducted was the administrative offices of the Almanzor Aguinaga Asenjo National Hospital in Chiclayo; b) The researcher introduced himself, identified himself by name and explained the title and objective of the research; c) The informed consent form was read; d) The staff members accepted and signed the informed consent form and were asked if they were willing to collaborate with the research; e) The interview began with the staff members who accepted; f) The interview was recorded using audio equipment; g) The interview ended with the equipment being turned off; and h) The interviewee was thanked for his or her attitude and willingness to participate.

The interview was not a simple conversation but an exchange of experiences and knowledge (Abad et al., 2010). There was an atmosphere of respect and understanding for the person (Bonill, 2008), and the communicative skills used were in appropriate language, without

technicalities (Fornells, 2009). Before the interview, it was necessary to identify their name and signature while maintaining anonymity (Robles, 2011). Criteria used were: a) Credibility, the results are credible and the data can be contrasted through documentary analysis, group discussion and triangulation (Lincoln and Guba, 1985); b) Auditability, what was collected can be confirmed with reality so that another researcher can follow the trail of what was investigated in public integrity and c) Transferability or applicability, with which it is possible to expand the results of the study to a different context of analysis.

Results and Discussion

From the semi-structured interviews with seven officials, six have experience in the public sector and work in Social Health Insurance; all worked during the Covid-19 health emergency. As a result of the analysis, the following categories and subcategories were obtained:

Figure 1 Categorization of qualitative data

Note: Prepared by the authors.

Regarding the specific objectives 1 and 2, after the interview with the interviewees, the information was reduced using extracts to reveal and interpret the results as detailed below:

1. The dissemination of ethics and integrity; in the offices where they work, there is little dissemination, there is little commitment to implement it; there is little presence of the Integrity Office of the institution to disseminate the guidelines; they have only been sent by e-mails and most of them have had to read them on their own, but there are many who are unaware of the documents such as the plan and the integrity and anti-corruption policy.
2. The behavior of the officials has deteriorated. It does not obey the training that a public official should have. It has become a habit not to respect each other; there are personal interests and attempts to corrupt; there are family members, cronyism, and there is no control and ethical conduct; they enter to take advantage, imposing the law of the strongest, there is disunity among coworkers and lack of communication. During the health emergency, there was an official whose behavior attracted attention; she tried to direct the contracting processes outside the norms, restricting access to supervise the works being executed; instead of protecting the institution's interests, she protected the interests of the suppliers. The assistant and administrative workers took advantage of the fact that the health emergency regulations protected vulnerable people; they took advantage of this benefit to not go to work, however; they went out and had a social life, and they went on trips, to parties, they worked in their clinics in a face-to-face way.

3. The appointment of officials; it is the responsibility of the highest level officials to have trained and suitable officials for open and transparent management; there is a difference between the official who enters to work by merit and the one who enters by hand; as their work is more transparent and efficient; unlike officials with poor ethics that in the future seek to gain and take advantage inappropriately, so it is convenient for some high-level officials to appoint officials questioned for inappropriate purposes so that they are more vulnerable to be convinced for their purposes. The appointment of officials is made by hand because they are positions of trust, party politics, friendship or because they are fellow students. Most of them come to learn because they do not know the mission of the institution, meritocracy is not promoted, some do not meet the profile, have criminal records, and there is no evaluation; many passes through the institution but do not leave history because the appointment of positions has been politicized.
4. During the pandemic, an official arrived with the suppliers, the contracts were split and then regularized, and a company was hired to implement a hospital for patient care Covid - 19, whose work was not completed or delivered and the hospital did not fulfill the public purpose. Likewise, some suppliers seek to corrupt the official in such a way that both have ethical responsibility; there were contracts without requirements, and they said that since it was a sanitary emergency, everything was justified and not auditable; logistic processes were not carried out as they should have been.
5. Support for ethical behavior; they reported little support from their immediate bosses; they say that it has not been a good experience because people who act ethically and with integrity label them as problematic people, making their opinion unimportant; some prefer not to speak or report for fear of reprisals, many are silent in collusion with the wrongdoing, there was a feeling of lack of support; lack of support from the highest level official, in some cases, officials have been forced to resign because they disagree with the fractioned purchases.
6. The anti-corruption system does not punish the corrupt; corruption is favored because the anti-corruption system is discredited. Corruption occurs from higher to lower hierarchy from the highest authority trying to circumvent controls. Some officials enter the entity with the idea of profiting and accepting a position because they have to pay political favors for being appointed; some try to join a group to obtain benefits and, in some cases, arrive and position themselves in the positions. There is corruption, but there are no sanctions, so they seek to evade responsibility and not do their job.
7. During the health emergency within the framework of Public Integrity, some higher-ranking officials sought out lower-ranking officials to demand the hiring of a certain person with names and surnames or for them to give their consent; the person who reports situations that violate ethics and integrity is relegated. There is pressure to hire workers because the positions are politically appointed; officials offered to hire workers' relatives as long as they supported them, which led to disunity.
8. During the health emergency, there was a tendency to choose a group of suppliers in advance to whom the contracts would be awarded; the suppliers look for officials and offer them gifts, the supplier being one of the main corruptors and when the official is not well trained he falls into corruption. In the case of hiring personnel to work in the institution, they cannot get a job because they do not have someone to support them.
9. There were feelings of indignation and discomfort; upon learning of officials who were caught receiving bribes from a supplier, they reported that it was shameless because logistics officials were talking on the phone with the suppliers and had already published them in flyers and disseminated them through social networks. So it causes indignation, and discomfort because it influences, and damaging the work they have

- been doing and that embarrasses everyone for being part of the institution; there were feelings of a broken spirit, but also fear that reporting can bring negative consequences to keeping their job in the institution.
10. The actions during the pandemic. Due to the priority of having medicines and medical equipment or infrastructure in the face of the urgent need of the patients affected with Covid-19 was such that it was necessary to act quickly without measuring the consequences that the contracting might have been directed. There were cases of contracting for overpriced infrastructure works that did not fulfill the public purpose. Due to the pandemic, suppliers took advantage of the desperation of the people in the situation and the emergency; they sold at high prices.
 11. Actions to promote integrity. Forms of free access to denounce acts of corruption should be established, and the selection of officials by meritocracy. They should be made aware of integrity by reflecting on the purpose of the public service for which they have been hired, and training should be carried out. The administrative, civil and criminal records of those hired should be verified.

In relation to specific objective 3, the background, theories and methodology have been triangulated on the following:

The dissemination of the integrity and anti-corruption policy is a function of the officials, when it is put into practice, it improves the behavior of the servant; it should not be expected that ethical rules exist but that the officials act out of duty (Canales, 2002). The appointment of officials is the responsibility of senior management; they are available to perform open and transparent management. Diaz (2018) refers to importance when based on ethics and governance. Officials who put ethics and integrity into practice are based on just principles (Rawls, 1971). On the part of officials, integrity practices were disrupted by the intention to direct contracting. When an official directs a procurement, it is considered an abuse of power for profit (Huberts et al., 2022). Corruption is a negative phenomenon in state institutions, causing significant damage, and affecting stability, democratic values, national security, and social and democratic principles (Inshyn et al., 2021).

Civil and public servants felt little support; they were labeled as problematic people and therefore preferred not to speak out of fear of losing their jobs. As a result, the public worker felt vulnerable to hurt and suffered harm (Ausín 2019). The control and anti-corruption system are weak. It does not punish the corrupt; they try to encourage people to do something irregular; it breaks the scheme that corruption is for self-interest, and pressure is exerted on people (Olli, 2017). Having experienced that officials exerted pressure on others and intervened in such acts of favoring the contracting of companies, suppliers took advantage of the situation by paying overpriced costs because of the pandemic.

Corruption is a problem that weakens democracy, which must be curbed through control mechanisms (OECD, 2018). There were feelings of indignation and discomfort with acts committed by officials. It is essential to promote public integrity through complaint mechanisms and raise awareness and training; coincidentally with the Humanist Theory of administration, which revalues human capacity, Mendoza (2018) conceives the human being as an individual or collective creation and construction. The theory of good governance is relevant, as are the actions of public servants and public officials (Van Stadem, 2022).

Specific objective 4, related to the design of a theoretical model, is intended to solve corruption problems that influence public integrity policy and affect the quality of care for

Social Security Health Insurance policyholders under a behavioral economics and ethical governance approach.

Proposed theoretical model

The research aims to solve anti-corruption problems that influence the behavior of employees and collaborators. Its general objective is to “Strengthen the preventive and sanctioning capacity against acts of corruption, through the identification and management of risks that affect integrity, generating management processes and action plans that lead to the improvement of public service in the Social Health Insurance”. As specific objectives: (i) Establish the philosophical, theoretical and legal foundations based on the approach of behavioral economics and ethical governance, preventing and strengthening the preventive capacity, identifying and managing risks against acts of corruption within the framework of public integrity; ii) Design the methodology of management processes and action plan with strategic axes, objectives and activities to help strengthen preventive and punitive capacity, as well as to identify and manage risks of acts of corruption; and iii) Contribute to prevent, identify and manage risks, with a disciplinary and control system to address alleged acts of corruption committed by officials or civil servants.

Figure 2 Graphical Representation of the Theoretical Model:

Source: Own elaboration.

In relation to specific objective 5 of the validity of the theoretical model, experts with PhDs in public management and/or research have been consulted, for which an instrument has been prepared to validate the theoretical model proposal, which contains criteria such as general aspects of the proposal, the structure and graphic representation, the development of the proposal and the integral perception of the proposal.

Conclusions

The following conclusions were reached:

1. Regarding the experiences that officials went through during the Covid-19 health emergency, they revealed situations related to behavior; having obtained findings such

- as the poor culture of integrity, appointment of officials without taking into account meritocracy, hiring practices, not in line with public integrity, little support for actions within the framework of ethics, the weakening of the anti-corruption system and the poor dissemination of ethical culture and integrity.
2. After interpreting the experiences of the officials, factors were identified that, according to the perspective of the officials, affect their behavior within the framework of public integrity, such as the pressures received by officials of higher hierarchical level to maintain their position, which caused them feelings of indignation and discomfort; during the pandemic. At first, it went unnoticed due to the urgency of the immediacy of having the medicines, medical material to attend patients affected by Covid-19, in some cases more expensive.
 3. Theoretical and methodological foundations were identified to support the proposal of a theoretical model from the approach of behavioral economics and ethical governance, based on the categories and subcategories, finding coincidences with the antecedents and theories of integrity policy.
 4. A theoretical model proposal was designed to help strengthen the preventive and sanctioning capacity in the face of acts of corruption, first by identifying and managing the risks that affect the integrity and then by generating management processes and action plans that lead to the improvement of public service in the Seguro Social de Salud (Social Health Insurance).
 5. Professional experts validated the theoretical model based on behavioral economics and ethical governance with doctoral degrees, who considered that the model presented was adequate in terms of graphic representation, content development and structure of the proposal.

References

- Abad, E., Delgado, P., & Cabrero, J. (2010). La investigación-acción-participativa. Una forma de investigar en la práctica enfermera. *Invest. educ. enferm*, 464-474.
- Acuerdo Nacional. (2021). 35 políticas del Estado del Acuerdo Nacional. Lima: CEPAL.
- Agenda 2030, O. (2015). Transformar nuestro mundo: la Agenda 2030 para el Desarrollo Sostenible. Naciones Unidas: Asamblea General.
- Arroyo Zavala, O. E. (2011). *Ética Pública Revalorando el Servicio Público*. Ciudad de México: Tecnológico de Monterrey.
- Ausín, T. (2019). Ética pública para generar confianza. *Revista Vasca de Gestión de Personas y Organizaciones Públicas*, 30-39.
- Barzelay, M. (2003). La Nueva Gerencia Pública: invitación a un diálogo cosmopolita. *Gestión y Política Pública*, 240-251.
- Barnacle, R. (2004). Reflection on Lived Experience in Educational Research. *Educational Philosophy and Theory*, 57-67.
- Bevir, M. (2009). *Key concepts in governance*. England: Sage.
- Bonill, C. (2008). La importancia de las habilidades comunicativas en la humanización de los cuidados. *Index Enferm*, 17(1):74-5.
- Bovarid, T., y Loffter, E. (2003). Evaluating the quality of public governance: Indicators, models and methodology. *International Review of Administrative Sciences*, 313-328.
- Canales, J. (2002). Algunas reflexiones sobre la ética pública. VII Congreso internacional del CLAD sobre la reforma del Estado y de la administración pública. Lisboa, Portugal: VII Congreso CLAD.
- Columbié, M. (2017). *Administración Pública. Conceptos y realidades*. Panamá: Ruth Casa Editorial.

- Contraloría, P. (2022). Portal Electrónico de CGR. Obtenido de Nota de Prensa N° 732-2022-CG/GCOC: <https://acortar.link/ALJB3k>
- Diaz Ortega, C. H. (2018). Gestión Pública del Siglo XXI y sus pilares principales: ética y gobernanza. *Revista Colombiana de Contabilidad*, 105-119.
- Diego Bautista, O. (2018). La Construcción de la Ética Pública en México en el inicio del siglo XXI. *Revista Internacional "Transparencia e Integridad"*, 1-12.
- Esteban Nieto, N. T. (2018). Tipos de Investigación. *Alicia*, 1-4.
- Essalud, P. (2019). Oficina de Integridad. Obtenido de Normativa: <https://acortar.link/BOxcBV>
- Ferrando, A. (2016). Guía de Economía del Comportamiento Vol. 1: Políticas Públicas. En A. Ferrando, *Contribuciones de la Economía del Comportamiento a la batalla contra la corrupción* (pág. 105). Mexico: Instituto Mexicano de Economía del Comportamiento.
- Fornells, J. (2009). El ABC del Mini-CEX. *Educ. méd*, 12(2):83-9.
- Fukuyama, F. (2016). Governance: What do we know, and how do we know it? *Annual Review of Political Science*, 89-105.
- Guba, E., & Lincoln, Y. (2002). *Paradigma Competencia en la Investigación Cualitativa*. Newbury Park: Sage.
- Hajer, M., Van Tatenhove, J., & Laurent, C. (2004). *Nieuwe vormen van governance*. Bilthoven, The Netherlands: RIVM.
- Hennings Otoyá, J. A. (2020). Corrupción En Las Contrataciones Del Estado: El Nefasto Club De La Construcción En El Perú. *Quipukamayoc*, 87-94.
- Hernández Sampieri, R., & Mendoza Torres, C. P. (2018). *Metodología de la Investigación*. México: MCGRAW-HILL INTERAMERICANA EDITORES, S.A.
- Herrera, R. (2016). ¿Buena Gobernanza Contra Buen Gobierno? *Revista Venezolana de Análisis de Coyuntura*, 289-294.
- Hoekstra, A., Huberts, L., & van Montfort, A. (2022). Content and Design of Integrity Systems: Evaluating Integrity Systems in Local Government. *Public Integrity*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10999922.2021.2014204>
- Hoekstra, A., & Kaptein, M. (2014). Comprender los procesos de formación de políticas de integridad. *Integridad Pública*, 243-264. doi:10.2753/pin1099-9922160302
- Honderich, T. (2013). De la ética. *Compendio de entradas de la Enciclopedia Oxford de Filosofía*. Madrid: Tecnos.
- Hospital Almenara. (2019). Obtenido de Fuera Los Corruptos Del Hospital Almenara: <https://acortar.link/iFVAsd>
- Huberts, L., Kaptein, M., & de Koning, B. (2022). Integrity Scandals of Politicians: A Political Integrity Index. *Public Integrity*, 24(3), 329–341. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10999922.2021.1940778>
- Huberts, L. (2014). La integridad de la gobernabilidad. Palgrave Macmillan. doi:10.1057/9781137380814
- Huberts, L., & Six, F. (2012). Sistemas de integridad local. *Integridad Pública*, 151-172. doi:10.2753/pin1099-9922140203
- Huberts, L., Kaptein, M., & Koning, B. (2022). Integrity Scandals of Politicians: A Political Integrity Index. *Public Integrity* 24 (3), 329-341. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/10999922.2021.1940778>
- Inshyn, M. I., Basai, O. V., Basai, N. M., Soroka, O. O., & Stremenovskyi, S. M. (2021). Prevenir y combatir corrupción (crimen económico): Ejemplos de gobernanza de la UE y Ucrania. *Revista Internacional de Gestión*, 532-544.
- Jimenez Asensio, R. (2017). Cómo prevenir la Corrupción: Integridad y Transparencia. *Revista Internacional de éticas aplicadas* n° 27, 405-409.

- Jolly, J. (2005). Gobernabilidad territorial y descentralización en Colombia: ¿Regir el territorio o gobernar los territorios? A propósito del política pública e descentralización en Colombia entre 1982 y 2002. *Papel Político*, 137-154.
- Kahneman, D., & Smith, V. (2002). Fundamentos de Economía del Comportamiento y Economía Experimental. *Cuestione Económicas*, 185-211.
- Kersbergen, K., & Van Waarden, F. (2001). Shifts in governance: Problems of legitimacy and accountability. Den Haag, The Netherlands: NWO.
- Lasthuizen, K., Huberts, L., & Heres, L. (2011). How to measure integrity violations. Towards a validated typology of unethical behavior. *Public Management Review*, 383-408.
- Levering, B., & Van Manen, M. (2002). Phenomenological Anthropology in the Netherlands and Flanders. *Phenomenology World-Wide*, 274-286.
- Lincoln, Y., & Guba, E. (1985). *Naturalistic Inquiry*. Beverly Hills: Sage Publications.
- Llanes Font, M., & Salvador Hernández, Y. (2018). Convergencia de la ética pública y los Objetivos de desarrollo sostenible: resorte subjetivo valioso. *Revista Dilemas Contemporáneos*, 1-28.
- Maldonado Melendez, M. A. (2018). Las contrataciones públicas y la buena gobernanza: Hacia la construcción de un derecho fundamental en el Perú e Iberoamérica. *SSRN Electronic Journal*, 1-31.
- Mari, R., Bo, R., & Climent, C. (2010). Propuesta de análisis fenomenológico de los datos obtenidos en la entrevista. *Revista de Ciències de Educació*, 1:113-33. Obtenido de <http://doi.org/b9qs>
- Mendoza, X., & Vernis, A. (2008). El Estado relacional y la transformación de las administraciones públicas. Catalunya: Administración Pública de Catalunya.
- Mendoza, J. (2018). Epistemología de la administración: objeto, estatuto, desarrollo disciplinar y método. *Pensamiento y Gestión*, 211-238.
- Modzom, V. (2017). Las Estrategias de Buena Gobernanza. *Citius, Altius, Fortius*, 7-12.
- Molano, M. (2016). Guía de Economía del Comportamiento. Instituto Mexicano de Economía del Comportamiento, 6-8.
- Monteduro, F., Cecchetti, I., Lai, Y., & Allegrini, V. (2021). Does stakeholder engagement affect corruption risk management? *Journal of Management and Governance*, 759-785.
- Noël Roth, A. (2019). Las políticas públicas y la gestión pública: un análisis desde la teoría y la práctica. *Estudios de la Gestión Revista Internacional de Admistración*, 223-229.
- OCDE Perú, E. (2018). Estudio de la OCDE sobre Integridad en el Perú. Lima: OECD.
- Olivera Robles, D., Nettel Barrera, A., & Aguado Romero, G. (2017). La Gobernanza y la Buena Administración en el Contexto del Control de la Inactividad Administrativa. *Ciencia Jurídica*, 119-136.
- Olli, H. (2017). The historical origins of corruption in the developing world: a comparative analysis of East Asia. *Crime Law Soc Change*, 145-165.
- Oyango, G. (2021). Whistleblowing behaviours and anti-corruption approaches in public administration in Kenya. *Economic and Political Studies*, 9(2), 230-254. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/20954816.2020.1800263>
- Palacios, D., & Corral, I. (2010). Fundamentos y desarrollo de un protocolo de investigación fenomenológica en enfermería. *Enferm Intensiva*, 21 (29): 68-73.
- Palacios Garay, J. P., Toledo-Córdova, M. F., Miranda-Aburto, E. J., & Flores Farro, A. (2021). Políticas públicas y gobernanza participativa Local. *Revista Venezolana de Gerencia*, 26(95), 564-577. doi:<https://doi.org/10.52080/rvgluz.27.95.8>
- Peters, G. (2010). Governance as political theory. *Jerusalem Papers en Regulation & Governance*, 1-22.
- Polo, L. (2003). *La esencia de la persona humana*. Pamplona: Eunsa.

- Ponce, H. (2019). La contratación pública responsable. Diseño de indicadores de medición. *Revista de Economía Publica, Social y Cooperativa*, 253-280.
- Portal Martínez, J. (2016). Control Interno e Integridad elementos necesarios para la gobernanza pública. *EL Cotidiano*, 7-13.
- Prado, E. (2022). El contrato millonario del primo de Jorge Pérez. *Diario La República*.
- Puello-Socarrás, J. F. (2018). Gobernanza y nueva Gestión Pública para la Paz. *REAd Porto Alegre*, 31-49.
- Restrepo Guzman, J. A. (2017). La Gestión Pública en la rama de la administración de justicia en Colombia, una mirada desde la teoría de la gestión y la teoría institucional. *Revista Ensayos*, 87-85.
- Reyes Fernández, N., & Ortiz Hernández, M. (2018). Gestión Pública y Ciudadanía: Una Reflexión en torno a las teorías sobre la democracia. *Administración y Desarrollo*, 114-137.
- Robles, B. (2011). La entrevista en profundidad: una técnica útil dentro del campo antropológico. *Cuicuilco*, 18(52):39-49.
- Rose-Ackerman, S. (2017). What does “governance” mean? . *Governance* doi:10.1111/gove.12212., 23–27.
- Rothstein, B., & Sorak, N. (2017). Ethical Codes for the Public Administration. *A Comparative Survey*. QoG Working Paper Series, 12.
- Saavedra Guajardo, E., & Castro, R. A. (2007). La investigación cualitativa, una discusión presente. *Liberabit v.13 n.13*, 63-69.
- Sánchez Chávez, E. (2018). Aplicaciones de la Economía del Comportamiento al diseño de políticas públicas. *Derecho y Economía Conductual*, 181-192.
- Sánchez, F., & Liendo, N. (2020). *Manual de Ciencia Política y Relaciones Internacionales*. Bogotá: Fondo de Publicaciones de la Universidad Sergio Arboleda.
- Silverman, E. (2018). *Methodological Investigations in Agent-Based Modelling*. Springer Open, 1-247
- Svitlana, K., Tetiana, H., & Vainius, S. (2019). Institutionalisation of Behavioural Insights in Public Policy . *VIEŠOJI POLITIKA IR ADMINISTRAVIMAS PUBLIC POLICY AND ADMINISTRATION*, 95-113.
- Taller, I. (2017). *Taller de Investigación Cualitativa*. Investigación Cualitativa. Obtenido de Universidad Alberto Hurtado: <https://goo.gl/LelRk>
- Tamayo y Tamayo, M. (1999). *Aprender a Investigar - Módulo 2 La Investigación*. Santa Fe de Bogotá: ICFES.
- Tapia Cachay, L. M., Couto, G., Pimentel, P., & Castanho, R. A. (2022). Internal Control and Its Application in Public Management: a Literature Review. *WSEAS TRANSACTIONS on BUSINESS and ECONOMICS*, Volume 19, 326-337. doi:DOI: 10.37394/23207.2022.19.29
- Trommell, W. (2020). Good Governance as Reflexive Governance: In Praise of Good Collegueship. *Public Integrity*, 227-235.
- Troncoso Pantoja, C., & Amaya, P. A. (2017). Entrevista: guía práctica para la recolección de datos cualitativos en investigación de salud. *Revista de la Facultad de Medicina*, 65(2):329.
- Valeriano Ortiz, L. F. (2019). Transparencia en la gestión pública y privada del Perú frente a la crisis de valores que afecten el desarrollo del país. *Gestión del Tercer Milenio*, 31-43.
- Van Stadem, R. (2022). Blind Spots in Public Ethics and Integrity Research: What Public Administration Scholars Can Learn from Aristotle. *Public Integrity*, 236-244.
- Vardi, Y., & Weitz, E. (2004). *Misbehavior in organizations. Theory, research, and management*. England: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.

Zamora Leclére, J. (2009). Ética de la Función Pública y Buen Gobierno. Obtenido de Mesa de Concertación para la Lucha contra la Pobreza:
<http://www.mesadeconcertacion.org.pe>